

The Theory of Perceived Legitimacy: Synthesizing the Theoretical Branches of European Union Legitimacy Research

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Abstract

This article is focused on two competing strains of legitimacy research in the European Union, taking as an example the discourse regarding the democratic deficit of the European Commission and the conceptualization of the EU as a regulatory state and not a democracy. The focus on the legitimacy of the European Commission is pressing due to the sudden rise in already established totalitarian tendencies in the European Union that were only hastened by the COVID-19 pandemic. The paper addresses the issue of how the European Commission is legitimizing itself when it's not composed of directly elected members, by engaging with the democratic deficit theory and the regulatory state theory. By exploring the perception of EU legitimacy, this article can further the debate on what non-state actors and non-institutional actions can do to influence the EU's legitimacy and the future of its democracy.

Keywords

European Union; European Commission; legitimacy; democratic deficit

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“Modern industrial civilization has developed within a certain system of convenient myths. (...) Now, it's long been understood very well that a society that is based on this principle will destroy itself in time. (...) In this possibly terminal phase of human existence, democracy and freedom are more than values to be treasured, they may well be essential to survival” (Noam Chomsky, 1995).

Introduction

Chomsky argues in the passage above that humans pervade myths to justify certain behaviors and political structures. In the long term, the prevailing hegemony of neoliberal governance found in the modern world, he argues, will undermine advanced capitalist societies and result in catastrophe if left to its own demises. Chomsky warns us not to blindly accept that a current institutional design is ethical; no system of authority is self-justifying. Chomsky encourages citizens to critically evaluate current paradigms of authority through democracy and any prevailing myths about their rule, and ask whether these systems are, in fact, legitimate. The legitimacy of a system is neither an independent nor a static fact, but a complex term describing a complex relationship between bodies and individuals in a political system. It's broadly assumed that the legitimacy of a system remains if the consensus on its rule is permissive (Hooghe & Marks, 2009).

However, any consensus will remain permissive if it is left unchallenged. Although one might not agree with Chomsky's apocalyptic vision of the future of modern neoliberal democracies, one should refrain from dismissing his diagnosis entirely. Particularly researchers in the field of European governance should take heed to reject such a warning. If we're unable or unwilling to challenge the prevailing idea that there's consensus on the European Union's legitimacy, its neoliberal economy, its democratic regime, and the problems associated with contemporary representative democracies, we might unknowingly prevent ourselves from discoveries, information and knowledge that could uncover a continuously self-destructive process leading to the dissolution of the European Union (EU).

Up until 1992, the European integration process had been, by and large, legitimized by the notion of a neo-liberal “permissive consensus” among the public that sanctions the workings and strategies employed by the European Commission (Hooghe & Marks, 2009). However, after several judicial and even popular challenges appeared following the referendums on and the ratification of the Maastricht Treaty, a steadily intensifying debate concerning the legitimacy of the European project and integration has embedded itself in both academic and public discourse. More than half of all EU citizens believe the EU will collapse within two decades (Crisp, 2019), and three quarters of eligible voters perceive their political system to be dysfunctional either at the national level, or at the EU level, or at both levels (Boffey, 2019).

Normative notions have prevailed in response to the legitimacy debate, which have only furthered normative reasoning in the analysis of terms, arguments and theories concerned with the understanding of the current state of European political governance, order, institutions and policies. This article is not concerned with institutional analysis, but with the often lucid and abstract of legitimacy as it is perceived by the citizens of a polity.

A continent in decline?

Institutional analysis and in-depth research on the functioning of the EU's actors are important. However, this article highlights an often-neglected aspect of EU research: whether or not the public perceives the European Union and the European Commission (EC) to be legitimate. Understanding what legitimacy means and how it can be measured in the context of the EU is necessary and important. Mainly, without a clear understanding of how legitimacy is granted, secured, and performed by a governing body, the EU will remain in a difficult position where it is unable to counter the adverse legitimacy claims of growing anti-democratic forces, such as totalitarianism, ultra-nationalism, and populism (Moghaddam, 2019). The rise of these regressive tendencies in the European integration process derives from EU citizens' skepticism towards the current governance regime of the EU and the problem of legitimate decision-making in a post-national context (Bosco & Verney, 2012).

Euroscepticism is both a symptom of a problem and a problem itself: it is both a creation of a prevailing sense of alienation by many of the EU's citizens due to the EU's "technocratic" regime, and it is the cause of further alienation by increasing populism and skepticism towards further integration (Bickerton & Accetti, 2015). Furthermore, the notion of an ever-closer EU seems less realistic when Europeanization no longer remains the preferred institutional model. Some are describing the current state of the European project as an increasingly differentiated EU (Leruth & Lord, 2015). This prospect is further worsened by the consistent attacks of populist and even fascist movements on European democracy. The rise of illiberal democracies in Poland and Hungary calls into question the degree to which ideas of pluralism, post-nationalism, and cosmopolitan pro-European attitudes are secure in the current day and age (Rupnik, 2016). The stability of EU's institutional design appears increasingly fragile as the last remnants of the post-communist wave of democratization disappear in a significant backlash of authoritarianism and nationalism that pervades large sections of Europe (Cianetti, et al, 2018). The 2019 (Treib, 2020) and 2024 (Marcos-Marne, 2024; Newell, 2024) EU Parliament elections and the national elections in-between have raised this issue higher on the agenda (Hess, 2024), to a point where many view the current trend as increasingly detrimental to EU's further development.

But why do people feel this way? What are their stories, their narratives, and their understandings? The issue of legitimacy seems to threaten the stability of the EU project. Regardless of how exaggerated the notion of a legitimacy crisis is or how fueled the discourse may be by views on either end of the debate, it is worth investigating these claims and exploring how the legitimacy of the EU is procured and accepted by the various actors on the European stage. As long as the EU is perceived to be illegitimate, the adverse forces of anti-democratic sentiments could erode a political project over 70 years in the making.

It should be noted that the focus on the legitimacy of the EC is pressing due to the sudden rise in already established totalitarian tendencies in the EU that were only hastened by the COVID-19 pandemic (Gerard & Mickler, 2021; Bargués & Morillas, 2021; Eliantonio & Ștefan, 2021; Schmidt, 2021). Following the literature review, there seems to be a knowledge gap in the field of European governance that deals explicitly with the measurement and study of legitimacy as a phenomenon of procurement. Although the literature does include studies that describe the EC as a driver for the stability and support of the EU (Hensell, 2022; Wolff, 2024) and other EU institutions (Greenwood & Roeder-Rynning, 2019), there is little research on how the EC legitimizes itself as a democratic entity when it's not composed of directly elected members.

To frame this research and limit a very broad topic to the dimensions of one article, this paper starts from a systematic review of two important theories on legitimacy in the field of European governance, with the goal of identifying the common ground between the theories, in order to further

the study of legitimacy while drawing upon the already established work in the field. By exploring the perception of EU legitimacy and the possible impurification of legitimacy, this article can further the debate on what non-state actors and non-institutional actions can do to influence the EU's legitimacy and the future of its democracy. The literature review included a wide selection of sources: articles concerning the legitimacy crisis of European democracy (Rensmann, 2019), books on the democratic empowerment of European citizens (Levi-Faur & van Waarde, 2018), discussion papers on how one should measure legitimacy in research (von Haldenwang, 2016), working papers concerned with legitimacy theories of the EU (Føllesdal, 2015), polls on citizen perceptions of the EU over time (European Parliament, 2019), and research on citizen education projects conducted by NGOs (Gong, 2020).

The historical legitimacy of the EU and the EC

If one seeks to understand the legitimacy of a political system, a good starting point seems to be discerning the legitimacy of the body responsible for the polity's agenda setting. Agenda setting refers to the degree to which a body, institution, or actor has the ability to influence the importance of select issues on behalf of the general public (McCombs & Reynolds, 2002). Issue salience and the awareness of certain issues are molded to accommodate a preconceived ideal hierarchy of importance within a polity. Although initially McCombs and Reynolds' theory described the influence media institutions have on public opinion, their definition of what agenda setting entails is highly functional in the study of EU legitimacy as it puts the focus on the degree to which the EC ensures control over issue salience and manages to procure legitimacy for their proposed hierarchy.

The historical development of the European integration project led to the EC ending up with a special privilege of having control over the EU's agenda setting (Haverland, et al, 2016). The EC is a depoliticized institution that argues for its legitimacy as the agenda setter of the EU from the presumption that the issues it is concerned with are better suited for technocratic governance. Instead of having directly elected officials, the EC instead relies on insight and expertise from members of interest group, academic institutions, and members of governments, as opposed to direct democratic input (Princen and Rhinard 2006; Pollack 1994; Wallace and Smith 1995).

The justification for this design has been the notion that there's a widespread public support for European integration in areas deemed unfit for direct democratic control, which legitimizes elite actors to act on the behalf of citizens in areas that are argued to require heightened expertise and competences. This zeitgeist is often described in the literature as the "permissive consensus" among EU citizens to allow technocratic decisions to be taken on their behalf (Hooghe & Mark, 2009). Through expert groups and depoliticized policy engineering, the EC has earned a reputation as a "purposeful opportunists" (Cram, 1993) in its pursuit of objectives and the fairly flexible activities through which it realizes its aims, and has throughout the years established itself as the preferred actor to solve certain EU issues declared to require expert governance, facilitated by its heightened credibility granted by reliance on specialists, civil servants and technocratic committees (Gornitzka and Sverdrup 2010; Haverland and Liefverink 2012; Kohler-Koch et al. 2013; Wille 2013). However, it is an existential problem if a system of governance that predicates itself on nondemocratic legitimacy ceases to be perceived as legitimate, and especially if this legitimacy is difficult to improve. This is a situation facing the EU, as the understanding of public support have moved away from a permissive consensus to an understanding of the EU as being plagued by "constraining dissensus".

The argument for the EC's privileged positions draws upon the accepted understanding of it having widespread support, and if said support for this design falters, the legitimacy of the polity will

naturally be called into question. This is precisely what is happening in the EU now. In the past decades, despite the increase of electoral participation in the Parliamentary elections of spring of 2019, there has been a steadily decreasing trust in EU and its institutions (Hooghe and Marks, 2009). In particular, the EC's supremacy devalues the other institutions' power and, in turn, their legitimacy. For instance, a parliament is supposed to act as the direct representation of a citizenry, standing in opposition to the judicial and executive branch of a liberal democracy. However, the European Parliament (EP) is not as representative as it could be due to the absence of an informed pan-European demos (Innerarity, 2014), and the inability of the EP to introduce new legislation (Kreppel & Webb, 2019). Despite the arguments for the creation of a second chamber in the EP to balance the powers between the EP and the EC (Young European Federalists, 2016), which would include representation of regions, cities, NGOs and other associations, the practicality of such propositions seems limited, especially seeing as the expansion of the Parliaments power remains uncertain (Dinan, 2018).

Furthermore, there are some questions about the necessity for a European "demos" in order to instill democratic legitimacy in the EU (Innerarity, 2014), although its absence is a valid point of critique. The accountability and legitimacy of the EC is subject to suffer if the people feel as if there is no democratic cohesion or equal representation across the EU, which has been especially illustrated in recent years. A contemporary example of this would be the surprising election of Ursula von der Leyen as the President of the EC in 2019. Her election effectively undermined and scrapped the Spitzenkandidat process (Gray, et al, 2019), a choice that further criticized the EP elections for not accommodating the EU's democratic values but rather showed preferences for politics "behind closed doors" (Stone, 2019). Seeing as von der Leyen was not elected by universal suffrage, her personal legitimacy was called into question too, a variation of the same skepticism that had already grown out of the dissatisfaction with the Spitzenkandidats not being voted on through universal suffrage in the first place (Macshane, 2018). The current balance of power is in the EC's favor, which renders the EP with a lacking capacity to effectively provide oversight and be a balancing power in relation to the EC.

Furthermore, whereas the member states frequently use public opinion in their construction of agenda setting, the public opinion is a fairly neglected area of research with relation to its impact on the EC and EU's agenda setting process (Princen, 2011). In order to counter this process, proponents of increased legitimacy of the EU argue in favor of increased deliberation and citizen empowerment (Suiter, et al, 2016). Some conceptualizations of legitimacy necessitate the inclusion of citizens in the multi-level governance and decision-making process (Abromeit, 1998), a notion many researchers have embraced in the study of EU legitimacy (Wiklund, 2015), Eising & Kohler-Koch, 1999), Lewi-Faur Dawid & Waarden, F. V., 2018). Despite increased support for this approach, the degree to which the EC has sought to include EU citizens in the agenda setting process in order to counter this decreasing trust seems to be lacking. For instance, the limited inclusion of surveys and other indicators of public opinion in the Directorates Generals' show this lacking improvement of the EU's legitimacy in the decision-making process (Haverland, et al, 2016). Existing studies also indicate that the expanded inclusion of other non-traditional actors and increased transparency in the governance system have not significantly increased the legitimacy of the EU or provided clear roles of participation of the new actors (Curry, 2016).

Is there a democratic deficit?

The first question then becomes: can this decreasing consensus be attributed to poor institutional design? By 1992 and the Maastricht Treaty's conception, certain decisions in the EU's development generated widespread concern for the creation of a possible democratic deficit. By merging the various

pillars of the EU, critics feared that erosion of national sovereignty would lead to a declining legitimacy of EU bodies and democratic elements.

There are five areas of concern to critics of the EU democratic development (Follesdal & Hix, 2006). Firstly, the continued integration of national and international institutions has led to the EU being a far greater executive power than the national state. The Court of Justice of the EU has developed, over the last decades, legal principles and case laws that influence social, political, and civil rights, to such a degree that it has determined the course of European integration more than democratic decisions made by the citizens of the member states. Secondly, this aforementioned development has shifted the balance of power between the EU and its member states' parliaments. For instance, one of the measures of the EU to deal effectively with the Euro-crisis was to undermine the national autonomy of member state parliaments with weaker economies. This imbalance favors the EP, effectively causing an imbalance between member states and the EU in terms of democratic control. And even though the EP has increased its powers, the agenda-setting ability of the EC stands paramount without directly elected officials. This means that national parliaments are weaker, and that the EP is too weak to justify this imbalance. Thirdly, citizens have shown a preference for national political issues in favor over EU wide concerns. The representatives elected to the EU bodies are chosen by their respective constituencies based on national concerns, leading to low trust in the EP and to national preferences still remaining the most important issue for citizens. Fourthly, the EU's institutions were originally designed to serve as technocratic bodies focusing on issue related to trade and the integrated market, a structural tradition that has yet to be fully democratized. Fifthly, the issues voted on and the preferences of EU citizens are rarely translated into actual policies, another indication of the lacking empowerment of EU citizens.

This perspective favors policy reform proposals that encourage direct democracy, deliberation, and reform of the EU institutions and criticism of representative democracy. Essentially, the conception of the EU as institutionally flawed can be explained if one defines legitimacy as granted by direct democratic participation. Claims to ethical authority must include some levels of citizen engagement throughout democratic procedures if said authority is to be perceived as legitimate. However, there are multiple perspectives on this analysis, and some criticism argues in favor of another perspective, which rejects the need for democratic legitimacy entirely.

The regulatory state

Some scholars, especially those inspired by Giandomenico Majone (Lodge, 2008), view the democratic deficit theory as misunderstanding the premise of EU legitimacy, arguing that the criticism predicates itself on a misunderstanding of the regulatory functions of the EU and the EC (Richardson, et al, 2015). They argue that the EU & EC should not be measured against the standards we apply to national democracies, as it is not a traditional democratic polity (Majone, 1997). Rather, the EU & EC are meant to be technocratic in design to serve the function of a transnational political body primarily concerned with the improvement and integration of the single market, and should therefore not be thought of as a system requiring democratic input to be legitimate, but as a system conducting regulatory actions in areas not concerned with democratic legitimacy (Majone, 2019, Moran, 2002; Braithwaite, 2013). A body focusing on primarily technocratic issues, such as the EC, requires a technocratic design structure in order to function properly. The EU & EC generate legitimacy precisely because their functions require primarily nondemocratic inputs. The EU's features are similar to those of a traditional democracy; however, the areas where it has the most influence and developed its most efficient instruments of governance are non-majoritarian by default, such as social and economic regulation.

However, these critics are in no way rejecting the discourse entirely and do acknowledge that there is a perception of a democratic deficit, and that this sentiment has been around for a while. Almost two decades ago, Scharpf (2002) began arguing that European integration and globalization had decreased the problem-solving capacity of the process' traditional actors. But instead of criticizing the non-democratic feature of the process, new actors and institutions such as the EC and the European Court of Justice are commended for their ability to create consensus in the EU on transnational issues and break deadlocks in the integration process (Héritier, 1999). Rather than agreeing that there are institutional flaws, this perspective shifts the focus from being concerned with institutional criticism to the issues of convergence, congruence, and perception of legitimacy as faith in authority. The problem is not that the EU is inherently illegitimate because its institutional design fails to live up to the standards set by traditional democratic nations; the issue facing the EU is a lack of legitimacy resulting from poor representation and education of its citizens on what the regulatory state is and what it is supposed to do (Moran, 2002). A contemporary example of the lacking comprehension of the EU's governance regime amongst ordinary citizens can be found in the United Kingdom. The day after the UK voted in the Brexit-referendum, the number one thing searched for on Google was "what is the EU?" (Cooney, 2016). If citizens are not able to understand the benefits and their own rights in a system, they will be inclined to be distrustful of the system's development which might manifest a preference for other alternatives. This perspective on the discourse positions civic and civil organization, and increased communication between the EU & EC and its citizens about the functioning of the EU as solutions to the problem of a perceived democratic deficit.

A possible synthesis: the theory of perceived legitimacy

Studies on the legitimacy of the EU tend to be skewed towards two separate perspectives that can instead be thought of as two separate dimensions of the same issue. One perspective is that of the democratic deficit theory, which argues that the EU is inherently flawed in its design and development, and therefore lacks the necessary democratic legitimacy to justify its governance system. The second perspective argues against the first and presents the EU as not a primary democratic structure, but rather as a regulatory body that shouldn't be evaluated by the same standards as other liberal democracies. Rather, its legitimacy is dependent on its ability to fulfil its functions as a regulatory system that is primary concerned with the functioning and operation of the single market.

The synthesis of these two perspectives reveals that the core issue at hand seems to be a steadily prevailing consensus that the EU is suffering from, first and foremost, a perceived legitimacy deficit. This conclusion is drawn from the existing literature, which shows that both theories strive to identify the source and sustainability of the EU's legitimacy, and that there is, regardless of reason, a disconnect between the citizens of the EU and those that govern. This is the theory of perceived legitimacy, which argues that a polity succeeds in justifying its power structures as long as they are perceived to be legitimate, regardless of whether or not they truthful towards their citizens or whether or not the polity's institutional structure can be deemed ethical. As long as a polity is perceived to be legitimate, actors in the polity will act accordingly, regardless of whether or not the polity is legitimate. Authorities can most effectively execute their power and facilitate successful cooperation between the various actors in its system as long as their claim to power is perceived to be legitimate. This is because perception of authority as illegitimate decreases reason-based trust, enforced compliance and voluntary cooperation (Hofmann, et al, 2017). By identifying the overarching problem as one of perceived legitimacy, this article draws upon both theories and may therefore be applied as a convergence to the two.

The academic debate concerning the issue of legitimacy research has failed to counter the normative issues and the difficulties associated with operationalization of legitimacy as an empirical unit. There are two major shortcomings in the current attempts to empirically measure legitimacy (Von Haldenwang, 2016): the first is the limitation of research by focusing exclusively on a specific form of legitimacy in a specific context, such as the legitimacy of liberal, Western democratic polities with a rule of law. The second shortcoming is that other studies only measure regime support as opposed to the actual legitimacy of the regime, equating two concepts that aren't the same. Furthermore, one also needs to understand how legitimacy can be influenced in developing policy proposals to improve upon it. Further research should take these problems into consideration when furthering the study of legitimacy in the European Union and in political science in general.

Defining the issue of political legitimacy in the EU as being primarily about perception and the degree to which institutions are successful in their procurement of legitimacy from citizens of the EU lets us understand legitimacy as a dialogical and cyclical relationship between ruler and subjects. Polities, by their nature, seek to procure legitimacy from their subjects through various means (Weber, et al., 2013). The EU and EC do so through a wide array of what can be defined as modalities of legitimation (von Haldenwang, 2016). The problem for future research and development of this theory would be to define the means of measuring and turning this legitimacy into an empirical unit.

Figure 1. Two cycles of legitimation.

Source: von Haldenwang, 2016.

Further research on what constitutes a moral and functioning legitimacy cycle must continuously be modified and updated, as the conditions for legitimacy will be prone to significant changes as society and civilization develops. Regardless of this, extensive research on the contemporary legitimacy cycle of the EU would prove fruitful for further legitimacy research, and for policy proposal development for improvement on the current regime. Therefore, new research on the legitimacy issues of the EU should aim at exploring the not just the supply cycle of legitimation, which has been the focus of this article, but also look at the demand cycle, as shown in Figure 1.

This new research should probe into the various legitimation demands made by the public of the EU and then look at the performance of the government when evaluating the degree to which the demand has been met. This could be an institutional analysis, best suited for case studies of various departments of the European Commission and the EU, where one would first evaluate what demands of legitimation the public has, and then follow that up by studying how these demands are met in the specific institutions of the EU. These case studies should be long field studies where the researcher engages in institutional and organizational analysis, combined with in-depth interviews to map the structure and then evaluate the performance of the various bodies of concern. The research could also collect data through surveys, data for a baseline for identifying the various themes of legitimacy among the public, which then could be translated into public modalities of legitimation demands.

Rational (not permissive) consensus

Further studies, outside the scope of this article, on the legitimacy procurement of a polity hold special relevance to non-governmental organizations (NGOs) because they serve as vital intermediaries between the polity and its citizens, often bridging the gap left by politicized or bureaucratized institutions (Greenwood, 2007; Penjueli, 2015). Unlike member states or political parties, which are frequently driven by electoral incentives or national interests, NGOs claim to operate with a mission-oriented focus that prioritizes societal needs and public welfare, thus alleviating them of some of the stigma associated with formal political or governmental organizations (Baur & Palazzo, 2015; Gnes & Vermeulen, 2019).

Their relative independence enables them to foster grassroots engagement, enhance transparency, and provide critical feedback that reinforces the Commission's accountability. By collaborating with the EC on policy development and implementation, NGOs could help craft policies that resonate with public expectations, thereby bolstering the Commission's democratic legitimacy. As proclaimed "non-partisan actors" with broad societal reach (Brinkerhoff, et al., 2007), NGOs are uniquely positioned to mitigate the perception of the Commission as a distant or technocratic institution, ensuring its legitimacy evolves in tandem with the values and aspirations of European society. Understanding the legitimacy discourse as a discourse about public perception of legitimacy, one may better know where to begin to even out the balance between those that seek to procure legitimacy and those that grant it. NGOs can procure legitimacy for such work as they are available outside of the ramifications of the state and the EU's institutions by being a natural response by civil society to the limits of a polity's functioning (Kralj, 2021).

Naturally, this must be done correctly. The current relationship between EU institutions and NGOs has been lacking in order to ensure effective legitimacy procurement from the general populace (Hallstrom, 2007; Heidbreder, 2020), and improvement are likely necessary on an institutional level to improve this dynamic. Nevertheless, NGOs are uniquely situated to help build rational consensus between citizens and governing bodies (Eun, 2017). This could be the case for the European Commission's legitimacy as well, if one utilized NGOs' unique position to promote active citizenship education (Xiong & Li, 2020; Bourne & Tarozzi, 2020). Citizenship education empowers individuals to understand the roles, functions, and policies of the EC, enabling informed and reasoned support for its initiatives rather than passive acceptance. NGOs, with their deep community roots and expertise in advocacy, could be adept at translating complex EU policies into accessible information, fostering critical engagement and dialogue among citizens. This approach ensures that public support for the EC is based on shared values, transparency, and trust rather than blind deference (Marshall, 2021; Elinson & Gould, 2022). Furthermore, as recipients of the Commission's legitimacy procurement efforts—such

as funding, consultations, and partnerships—NGOs gain the tools to amplify these educational initiatives and act as legitimacy procurers themselves. By facilitating informed civic participation, NGOs strengthen the democratic legitimacy of the Commission, making them indispensable in bridging the gap between the institution and the public. Studying their role in citizenship education provides valuable insights into how legitimacy can be cultivated through active, participatory means, ultimately ensuring a more engaged and empowered European citizenry.

I suggest that NGOs further explores the emancipatory qualities of citizen education. Citizen education is as an expansion of communicative practice that develops our collective consciousness and drives the citizenry towards mutual understandings (Habermas, 1971). Through consistent citizen education one can facilitate and develop, through trial and error, means of communication and political channels that create not a permissive, but rather a rational consensus for the EU's and EC's rule. A rational consensus is different from the permissive consensus mentioned earlier, as it does not suppose that one is either contributing to a widespread census or a dissensus through evaluating the EU and EC's legitimacy. Rather, the citizens need to be adequately informed and capable of discerning on their own whether they think the EU & EC are legitimate before they can consent to be governed. In short, citizens must be made able to rationally consent to the rule of a complex polity. This perspective on citizenship states that to be a full citizen of a polity, one needs the means to claim one's rights. This formulation is important, as it keeps the most important unit of measurement in focus: the individual. Since this article identified the issue of legitimacy to be in practicality an issue of perception, NGOs should keep focusing on the ways in which they might inspire individuals to rationally engage with the political structures around them. NGOs can only hope to change the landscape of a vast polity by starting to foster a democratic culture at the bottom of the hierarchy, where they can inspire rational consensus from citizens by informing them of their rights, the means available to them, and the actual workings of their political system.

Conclusion

Rational consensus could be achieved if NGOs apply the following recommendations to their future citizen education projects. Firstly, NGOs must be aware of the current standard of civic education given to EU citizens in school and the policies of the current ruling regime. Regime shifts and changes in the political climate might impact the overall quality of civic and citizen education in schools and the educational system of member states. Awareness of the current state of citizen education in educational institutions makes it possible for them to fill the gaps or provide an otherwise neutral educational platform outside the realms of government influence.

NGOs are in a unique position to provide citizen education outside the ramifications of institutions, particularly in the role as a mediator between communities and schools. This position grants them great influence on citizens' development and of their understanding of what it entails to be a citizen. NGOs should, therefore, facilitate even more non-formal and informal citizen education targeting citizens in the EU, with a focus on those areas of concern to EU citizens. Educating citizens leads to a nuanced understanding of the EU, instead of a clear-cut support or rejection.

Secondly, NGOs' citizen education should take due regard of the social issues and challenges facing EU citizens. Literacy of their own system, be it either the ramifications of global economic forces on job opportunities in Croatia or the issues related to ethnic diversity and cultural differences, should take preference for general political education.

Thirdly, NGOs must continue to provide apolitical and nonideological citizen education that, as much as possible, engages the participants in decision-making based on already existing institutions. This ensures minimal bias and facilitates democratic culture instead of indoctrination.

Fourthly, NGOs must ensure that their staff is adequately skilled and trained to secure high quality citizen education projects. As mentioned before, regime shifts might greatly impede the development of citizen education skills in schools, which can reduce the level of skill among teachers to provide education of high quality. NGOs are particularly useful here, as they can not only teach pupils, but motivate the staff and teachers at the schools they collaborate with to improve their knowledge and invest more resources in democratic development. NGOs' staff can even encourage teachers at the schools they visit to the point that they find motivation to improve their own civic education courses by introducing some of NGOs' projects in their curriculum.

Finally, and maybe most ambitious, is to expand the pan-European network of NGOs using citizen education. Projects such as bEUcitizen (CORDIS, 2013) could serve as a model for how such international networks might be developed and end up looking like, and NGOs should explore the means available to them to collaborate with NGOs from other member states in the EU that might share their vision of developing a proper democratic culture in the EU.

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